

This article is made available by the Document Delivery Service of IRRI Library for personal scholarly, research, and educational use. Further distribution requires the permission of the copyright owner.

replications. At each site, the recommended doses of farmyard manure (5 kg/m²) and inorganic fertilizer (90-45-45 g NPK/m²) were applied before sowing. Pregerminated seeds of three varieties (IET6893, CTH1, and Mangala) were sown during 1st wk of December. The treatments comprised two types of seedbeds (raised and flat) and four seedbed conditions: control; nursery beds covered with rice straw at 5 t/ha; nursery beds covered with transparent polythene sheeting (300 gauge) at 45 cm above ground level, keeping the bed airtight for 15 d after sowing (DAS) and later exposing the seedlings to the natural environment; and a double dose of the

recommended P (88 kg/ha) applied before sowing.

Air temperature at 5 cm above the soil surface outside and under the covering and soil temperature at 5 cm below the surface were recorded every day for 15 DAS (Table 1).

Air and soil temperatures were approximately 20 °C in the control treatment. Covering the nursery beds with polythene sheeting increased seedling dry weight from 0.28 to 1.0 g, presumably as a result of the increased temperature.

In contrast, the lower soil temperature under the rice straw mulch resulted in a decline in seedling dry weight to 0.05 g.

A double dose of P increased seedling dry weight to 0.73 g without any significant change in soil temperature (Table 2). This suggests the most critical factor determining the growth rate of seedlings under low soil temperature conditions may be availability of an immobile nutrient such as P. Seedbed condition, raised or flat beds, nonpuddled or puddled condition, and not impounding or impounding water may also have influenced seedling height to a lesser extent in the double P treatment.

Using either polythene sheeting or applying P could provide 25-d-old seedlings suitable for transplanting in the Hill Zone. ■

Effect of planting date on grain yield and quality of semidwarf scented rice varieties

S. P. Singh, K. G. Pillai, D. Pati, and N. Shobha Rani, Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh (AP), India

With the release of semidwarf scented rice varieties, the optimum planting time had to be determined to exploit their grain yield potential while still maintaining grain quality.

Field experiments were conducted during 1990-91 wet seasons at the DRR experimental farm in Rajendranagar. The

clay (Vertisols) soil has low to medium available N and P with pH 8.2. Semidwarf scented varieties Haryana Basmati 1, Pusa Basmati 1, and Kasturi were tested with check variety Basmati 370 under three planting dates: 15 Jul, 25 Jul, and 4 Aug.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, with varieties in main plots and planting dates in subplots. A single dose of 22 kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha was applied along with three splits of the recommended N dose of 90 kg/ha: 45 kg as a basal dressing, 22.5 kg at tillering, and 22.5 kg at panicle initiation. Twenty-five-d-old seedlings (2-3/hill) were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing.

All three improved varieties were significantly superior over Basmati 370 during 1991, although differences among them were nonsignificant. Mean yield increase over that of Basmati 370 was 45.0% for Pusa Basmati 1, 42.2 % for Haryana Basmati 1, and 36.3% for Kasturi. A significantly linear reduction in grain yield was recorded with successive delay in planting from 3.8 t/ha from 15 Jul to 2.8 t/ha from 4 Aug. Average grain yield was reduced by 21.1% for 25 Jul planting and 27.8% for 4 Aug compared with the grain yield for 15 Jul planting. Daylight hours were maximum for the crop planted on 25 Jul. The maximum mean day temperature was

Grain yield and quality parameters of semidwarf scented rice varieties under different planting dates. DRR, Rajendranagar, AP, India. 1990-91 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Grain quality parameters ^a								
	1990	1991	Mean	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Kernel length (mm)		Elongation ratio	Alkali value	Amylose value (%) 1991	Aroma
							Before cooking	After cooking				
<i>Variety</i>												
Haryana												
Basmati 1	3.6	3.5	3.6	76.8	71.1	27.3	6.8	11.5	1.7	6.56-6.57	20.3	SS ^b
Pusa												
Basmati 1	3.5	3.8	3.6	75.5	70.6	33.8	6.6	12.4	1.9	5.65-5.67	20.3	SS
Kasturi	3.3	3.5	3.4	75.9	70.1	42.7	6.7	12.0	1.8	5.48-5.51	18.0	SS
Basmati 370	-	2.5	2.5	77.2	72.5	24.7	6.5	11.1	1.7	-	-	SS
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3										
<i>Planting date</i>												
15 Jul	3.6	4.0	3.8	76.4	71.0	28.8	6.6	11.3	1.7	5.72-5.80	20.5	SS
25 Jul	3.5	3.2	3.3	75.3	70.3	34.1	6.7	12.4	1.9	6.05-6.03	19.2	SS
4 Aug	3.0	2.6	2.8	76.5	70.8	40.8	6.8	12.3	1.8	5.88-5.92	19.4	SS
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3										

^aMean of 2 yr. ^bSS = strongly scented.

recorded for the 15 Jul planting, which accounts for its higher mean grain yield.

Hulling (77.2%) and milling (72.50%) percentages were highest for Basmati 370, though its head rice recovery was the lowest (24.66%). Haryana Basmati 1 showed maximum kernel length (6.8 mm) and intermediate amylose content (20.3%) while Pusa Basmati 1 exhibited the highest linear elongation of cooked rice (12.4 mm) and elongation ratio (1.9) coupled with an acceptable amylose content (20.3%). Kasturi recorded the highest head rice recovery (42.7%) (see table).

Among the different planting dates, maximum hulling (76.5%) and head rice recovery (40.8%) and highest kernel length (6.8 mm) were recorded for 4 Aug planting, although grain yield declined with delayed planting. Maximum kernel length after cooking (12.4 mm) and elongation ratio (1.9%) were recorded for 25 Jul planting, and high milling percentage (71.0) and intermediate amylose content (20.5%) were recorded for 15 Jul planting. Aroma was strong under all planting dates.

In general, late planting promoted significant improvements in grain quality characteristics but at the cost of slightly reducing grain yield. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Reprint service. All items included in the *Rice literature update* are available at the IRRI Library and Documentation Service. Photocopies of original documents (not to exceed 40 pages) are supplied free to rice scientists of developing countries. Rice scientists elsewhere are charged US\$0.20 for each page or part of a page copied, plus postage. Payment should be in check or money order, payable to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI.

Address requests to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. Fax: (63-2) 817-2087, electronic mail: C.AUSTRIA@IRRI.CGNET.COM

Integrated pest management—diseases

Comparison of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains from Africa, North America, and Asia by restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis

M. Ryba-White, Plant Pathology Department, Kansas State University, Manhattan, Kansas, USA; J. L. Notteghem, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrières, 34032 Montpellier Cedex, France; and J. E. Leach, Kansas State University, USA

Bacterial blight, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*), is a major

disease of rice in Asia. The disease also has been reported to occur in North and South America and Africa. Although the symptoms of the disease caused by strains from the various countries are similar, the aggressiveness of strains to susceptible rice cultivars varies. For example, the strains from North America are less aggressive than those from Asia, Africa, and South America.

We used restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis to compare the genomes of *Xoo* strains from Africa (strains CAMX01 and CAMX02 from Cameroon and MALX01, MALX02, and MALX03 from Mali) and North America (20 strains from

1. Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) patterns of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* from the Philippines (PX061 and PX086), Mali (MALX01), Cameroon (CAMX01), USA (TX57-5 and TX 13-5C), Japan (JXOT7133 and JXOH75373), India (IXO-10 and IXO-4), and Colombia (CIAT1186). Also included are *X. o. pv. oryzicola* strains BLS175 and BLS256. Southern blots of *EcoRI*-digested genomic DNA were probed with ³²P-labeled pBSavrXa10, which contains a 3.1 kb *Bam*HI fragment internal to avirulence gene *avrXa10*.

2. Same as Figure 1, except the blot was probed with pBS101, which contains the mobile insertion element IS1112 on 2.4 kb *EcoRI*-*Hind*III fragment.